

D2.1 Protein stability and folding proceedings

Name of project: Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern
Slovakia (**CasProt**)
No. 952333

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Deliverable No:	D.2.1.
Work package no. and title	WP2 Workshops, training & symposia
Task no. and title:	Task 2.1. Symposium on protein stability and folding
Nature:	ORDP : Open Research Data Pilot
Dissemination level:	Public
Lead Beneficiary:	UPJS
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Reviewer:	Prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlák, DSc. Prof. Dr. Matthias Rief
Date of publication:	30 th of September 2022

Document History

Date	Authors	Version
30 th of September 2022	Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, PhD. Abhigyan Sengupta, PhD.	1.0

APPROVALS

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ABBREVIATIONS

CRC	Collaborative Research Center
D2.1	Deliverable 2.1 of the CasProt project
M24	Month 24
TUM	Technical University Munich
UPJS	Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice
UZH	University Zurich

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A symposium on protein stability and folding was organized in Hohenkammer between 22-24.5.2022 and in Garching b. Munchen between 25-26.5. 2022. In Hohenkammer, 21 talks were presented by 12 invited principal investigators, six postdocs and 3 Ph.D. students. Principal investigators are part of the collaborative research center SFB863, devoted to forces in biomolecular systems. Each PI provides unique expertise and viewpoints on different aspects of biomolecules and their super assemblies. At the same time, experimental and theoretical approaches are combined to achieve a high level of synergy, as indicated by a strong publication track record. The number of early-stage researchers was 12, and the CasProt project was presented by project coordinator Assoc. prof. Erik Sedlak, co-investigator prof. Matthias Rief, as well as senior researchers Dr. Abhigyan Sengupta and Assoc. prof. Gabriel Zoldak and three PhD Students from University in Kosice: Veronika Dzurillova (f), Kristina Felcikova (f), and Michal Gala (m). After the first part of the symposium, the event moved to Garching, Center for Protein Assembly and continued with the introduction of laboratories in Kosice (see presentation attached). During the symposium, a new collaboration was established with prof. Martin Zacharias regarding the availability of their computing time at their high-performance cluster.

In summary, this report provides an overview of current challenges and hot topics in protein science. We are convinced that the report can help us focus on specific big questions that the protein community is currently discussing.

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1. SYMPOSIUM PROGRAM

Forces in **SFB**₈₆₃
Biomolecular Systems

CasProt

Final SFB-Meeting

BIOMOLECULAR MECHANICS (SFB 563)

and

SYMPOSIUM ON PROTEIN STABILITY AND FOLDING (CASPROT)

22.05. - 26.05.2022

Schloss Hohenkammer / Garching b. München

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Program

Sunday, 22.05.2022

Location: Schloss Hohenkammer, Schloßstraße 18-25, 85411 Hohenkammer, Germany

≈12:00 Arrival / Check-in / Dinner at the “Gutshof-Restaurant”, 1st floor

19:00 Dinner at “Gutshof-Restaurant”

Monday, 23.05.2022

Location: Schloss Hohenkammer, Schloßstraße 18-25, 85411 Hohenkammer, Germany

- 13:00 Welcome by Matthias Rief, “Gutshof-Saal”, 1st floor, Gutshof
- 13:15 [Prof. Dr. Petra Schwille, B10 Max-Planck-Institute of Biochemistry, Martinsried, Germany](#)
Talk title: Expected and unexpected forces in minimal cell division
- 13:45 [Dr. Massimo Kube A9, Dept. of Physics, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: Towards cyro EM of proteins under force
- 14:15 [Dr. Maximilian Kienlein A10, Dept. of Physics, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: Conformational dynamics and ligand binding of the SBD2 protein
- 15:00 Coffee Break at “Gutshof Foyer”
- 15:15 [Prof. Dr. Matthias Rief A2, Dept. of Physics, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: Single molecule mechanics of integrin-mediated cell adhesion
- 15:45 [Prof. Dr. Johannes Buchner A4, Dept. of Chemistry, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: How molecular chaperones shape proteins
- 16:45 Poster-Session “Gutshof-Saal”, PI-Meeting “Room Multimedia”
- 19:00 Dinner at “Gutshof-Restaurant”
- 21:00 cont. Poster Session “Gutshof-Saal”

Tuesday, 24.05.2022

Location: Schloss Hohenkammer, Schloßstraße 18-25, 85411 Hohenkammer, Germany

- 7:00 Breakfast and general discussions
- 9:00 [Prof. Dr. Friedrich Simmel A8, Dept. of Physics, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: Forces in DNA nanosystems – from pores to robots
- 9:30 [Prof. Dr. Jan Lipfert A11, Dept. of Physics, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: Using physics to understand and fight viruses
- 10:00 [Dr. Karl Duderstadt A12, Dept. of Physics, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: How shape and context regulate the chromosome reorganization dynamics of SMCs
- 10:30 Coffee Break at “Gutshof Foyer”
- 10:45 [Dr. Michael Isselstein A13](#)
Talk title: Linker molecules convert commercial fluorophores into tailored functional probes during biolabelling
- 11:15 [Dr. Timon Nast-Kolb B1, Dept. of Physics, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: VASP phase separates on lipid bilayers to induce polymerization driven actin bundle formation
- 11:45 [Dr. Timo Krüger B2, Faculty of Physics, LMU, Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: Condensed topological defects in weak active nematics
- 12:15 Lunch Break at “Gutshof Restaurant”
- 13:45 [Dr. Jakob Reber B3, Max-Planck-Institute of Biochemistry, Martinsried, Germany](#)
Talk title: Transmembrane domain mediated folding of integrin head domains
- 14:15 [Prof. Dr. Claudia Veigel B6, Institute of Physiology, LMU, Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: Mechanics and regulation of the molecular motor Myosin-VI
- 14:45 [Prof. Dr. Zeynep Ökten B8, Dept. of Physics, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: On the road with motor proteins
- 15:15 Coffee Break at “Gutshof Foyer”
- 15:35 [Prof. Dr. Job Boekhoven B11, Dept. of Chemistry, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: Chemically fueled molecular assemblies: from self-healing gels to the engineering of life
- 16:05 [Prof. Dr. Ulrich Gerland B12, Dept. of Physics, TU Munich, Germany](#)
Talk title: Nucleosome dynamics in gene regulation

Wednesday, 25.05.2022

Location: Center for Functional Protein Assemblies (CPA), Ernst-Otto-Fischer-Str. 8, D-85748 Garching, Germany

- 10:00 [Assoc. prof. Erik Sedlák, Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, TIP, PJ Safarik University in Kosice](#)
Talk title: Research topics in Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences in Košice
- 10:30 [Assoc. prof. Gabriel Žoldák, Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, TIP, PJ Safarik University in Kosice](#)
Talk title: Protein folding and stability – human myeloma light chain proteins
- 11:00 [Michal Gala, PhD student, Dep. Of Biophysics, Faculty of Sciences, PJ Safarik University in Kosice](#)
Talk title: In silico protein evolution
- 11:30 [Veronika Dzurillova, PhD student, Dep. Of Biophysics, Faculty of Sciences, PJ Safarik University in Kosice](#)
Talk title: Utilization of ribosome display in directed evolution of haloalkane dehalogenase DhaA
- 12:00 [Kristína Felcikova, PhD student, Dep. Of Biophysics, Faculty of Sciences, PJ Safarik University in Kosice](#)
Talk title: LOV2 domain as photosensitizer in photodynamic therapy
- 12:30 Lunch break
- 14:00 Lab tour Center for Functional Protein Assemblies (CPA)
- 19:00 Dinner at “Pizzeria Garching”

Thursday, 26.05.2022

Location: Center for Functional Protein Assemblies (CPA), Ernst-Otto-Fischer-Str. 8, D-85748 Garching, Germany

- 8:00 Farewell and departure

Wishing you inspiring talks

2. CONFERENCE TOPICS

2.1 Topic 1. Research topics in Collaborative Research Centre 863 - Munich

Mechanical forces affect and control many vital processes in cells. Examples include genome organization, cellular transport, cell motility, and cell development and differentiation. The question of how mechanical cues eventually lead to a complex biological response is still poorly understood despite its importance for many processes of biological and medical relevance. Uncovering the principles underlying molecular mechano-biology requires a multi-faceted approach that combines advanced single-molecule mechanical methods, in vitro reconstitution of biomolecular systems, imaging, and cell biology. In the past eight years, Collaborative Research Centre in Munich (CRC) has assembled a team of biophysicists, theorists, biochemists and cell biologists with the common goal of studying the effects of mechanical forces on biomolecular systems in an interdisciplinary approach. In the past, the researchers of this CRC have developed cutting-edge technologies to study biomechanical systems from the single-molecule level up to the cellular scale. Over this time, strong collaborations have evolved across the different projects, in which the combined expertise in physical technologies and advanced cell biology has resulted in synergies enabling research impossible to conduct for one research group alone. Many key developments within this CRC, like dynamic structure determination using FRET, deconvolution single-molecule force spectroscopy, DNA origami-based single-molecule devices or in vivo force sensors, had taken the research to a new level and will now enable experiments inconceivable at the time when this CRC had started. Now, researchers in this CRC use this momentum and tackle novel questions in biomolecular mechanics. In the first research area, they investigate biomechanics on the single-molecule level. Research topics include the dynamics and interaction of proteins and molecular machines studied by force spectroscopy and molecular dynamics calculations. A focus is also put on mechanical aspects of replication and packaging of DNA using DNA origami, magnetic tweezers, flow stretching, and MD simulations. The second research area studied mechanics on a supra-molecular and cellular scale. Mechanics of active cytoskeletal networks, molecular motors, and cell adhesion mechanics are the project's primary focus. This research provides us with in vitro models for the mechanics of essential processes like cell motility and division. This CRC has unraveled molecular foundations for many biomechanical processes relevant in the biological and medical sciences.

CRC Publications and selected abstracts of scientific publications:

M. Jahn, K. Tych, H. Girstmair, M. Steinmaßl, T. Hugel, J. Buchner, and M. Rief (2018). Folding and Domain Interactions of Three Orthologs of Hsp90 Studied by Single-Molecule Force Spectroscopy. *Structure*, 26 (1): 96-105.

Abstract

The heat-shock protein 90 (Hsp90) molecular chaperones are highly conserved across species. However, their dynamic properties can vary significantly from organism to organism. Here we used high-precision optical tweezers to analyze the mechanical properties and folding of different Hsp90 orthologs, namely bacterial Hsp90 (HtpG) and Hsp90 from the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) (Grp94), as well as from the cytosol of the eukaryotic cell (Hsp82). We find that the folding rates of Hsp82 and HtpG are similar, while the folding of Grp94 is slowed down by misfolding of the N-terminal domain. Furthermore, the domain interactions mediated by the charged linker, involved in the conformational cycles of all three orthologs, are much stronger for Grp94 than for Hsp82, keeping the N-terminal domain and the middle domain in close proximity. Thus, the ER resident Hsp90 ortholog differs from the cytosolic counterparts in basic functionally relevant structural properties.

B. Winkeljann, B.T. Käsdorf, J. Boekhoven, and O. Lieleg (2018). Macromolecular Coating Enables Tunable Selectivity in a Porous PDMS Matrix. *Macromol Biosci*, 18: 1700311.

Abstract

Whether for laboratory use or clinical practice, many fields in Life Sciences require selective filtering. However, most existing filter systems lack the ability to easily tune their filtration behavior. Two key elements for efficient filtering are a high surface-to-volume ratio and the presence of suitable chemical groups which establish selectivity. In this study, an artificial PDMS-based capillary system with highly tunable selectivity properties is presented. The high surface-to-volume ratio of this filter system is generated by first embedding sugar fibers into a synthetic polymer matrix and then dissolving these fibers from the cured polymer. To functionalize this filter, the inner surface of the capillaries is coated with purified or synthetic macromolecules. Depending on the type of macromolecule used for filter functionalization, selective sieving is observed based on steric hindrance, electrostatic binding, electrostatic repulsion, or specific binding interactions. Furthermore, it is demonstrated that enzymes can be immobilized in the capillary system which allows for performing multiple cycles of enzymatic reactions with the same batch of enzymes and without the need to separate the enzymes from their reaction products. In addition to lab-scale filtration and enzyme immobilization applications demonstrated here, the functionalized porous PDMS matrix may also be used to test binding interactions between different molecules.

M. Tena-Solsona, C. Wanzke, B. Riess, A.R. Bausch, and J. Boekhoven (2018). Self-Selection of Dissipative Assemblies Driven by Primitive Chemical Reaction Networks. *Nature Commun*, 9:2044, DOI: 10.1038.

Abstract

Life is a dissipative nonequilibrium structure that requires constant consumption of energy to sustain itself. How such an unstable state could have selected from an abiotic pool of molecules remains a mystery. Here we show that liquid phase-separation offers a mechanism for the selection of dissipative products from a library of reacting molecules. We bring a set of primitive carboxylic acids out-of-

equilibrium by addition of high-energy condensing agents. The resulting anhydrides are transiently present before deactivation via hydrolysis. We find the anhydrides that phase-separate into droplets to protect themselves from hydrolysis and to be more persistent than non-assembling ones. Thus, after several starvation-refueling cycles, the library self-selects the phase-separating anhydrides. We observe that the self-selection mechanism is more effective when the library is brought out-of-equilibrium by periodic addition of batches as opposed to feeding it continuously. Our results suggest that phase-separation offers a selection mechanism for energy dissipating assemblies.

P. Wilke, E. Reithmann, and E. Frey (2018). Two-species active transport along cylindrical biofilaments is limited by emergent topological hindrance. *Phys Rev X*

M. Rank, and E. Frey (2018). Crowding and Pausing Strongly Affect Dynamics of Kinesin-1 Motors along Microtubules. *Biophys J*, 115: 1068-1081.

F. Kriegel, Ch. Matek, T. Dršata, K. Kulenkampff, S. Tschirpke, M. Zacharias, F. Lankaš, and J. Lipfert (2018). The Temperature Dependence of the Helical Twist of DNA. *Nucleic Acids Research*, DOI: 10.1093.

L. Huber, R. Suzuki, T. Krüger, E. Frey, and A.R. Bausch Emergence of Coexisting ordered States in Active Matter Systems (2018). *Science*, 10.1126.

R. Maan, E. Loiseau, and A.R. Bausch (2018). Adhesion of Active Cytoskeletal Vesicles. *Biophys J*, 115: 2395-2402.

Abstract

Regulation of adhesion is a ubiquitous feature of living cells, observed during processes such as motility, antigen recognition, or rigidity sensing. At the molecular scale, a myriad of mechanisms are necessary to recruit and activate the essential proteins, whereas at the cellular scale, efficient regulation of adhesion relies on the cell's ability to adapt its global shape. To understand the role of shape remodeling during adhesion, we use a synthetic biology approach to design a minimal experimental model, starting with a limited number of building blocks. We assemble cytoskeletal vesicles whose size, reduced volume, and cytoskeletal contractility can be independently tuned. We show that these cytoskeletal vesicles can sustain strong adhesion to solid substrates only if the actin cortex is actively remodeled significantly. When the cytoskeletal vesicles are deformed under hypertonic osmotic pressure, they develop a crumpled geometry with deformations. In the presence of molecular motors, these deformations are dynamic in nature, and the excess membrane area generated thereby can be used to gain adhesion energy. The cytoskeletal vesicles are able to attach to the rigid glass surfaces even under strong adhesive forces just like the cortex-free vesicles. The balance of deformability and adhesion strength is identified to be key to enable cytoskeletal vesicles to adhere to solid substrates.

M. Klotz, M. Kretschmer, A. Goetz, S. Ezendam, O. Lieleg, and M. Opitz (2019). Importance of the Biofilm Matrix for the Erosion Stability of *Bacillus subtilis* NCIB 3610 Biofilms. *RSC Adv.*, 2019, 9, 11251.

B. Rogez et. al (2019). Reconstitution reveals how myosin-VI selforganises to generate a dynamic mechanism of membrane sculpting. *NatureComm*, 2019, 10:3305 | <https://doi.org/10.1038>.

R. Mächtel, A. Narducci, D.A. Griffith, and Thorben Cordes (2019). An Integrated Transport Mechanism of the Maltose ABC Importer. *ResMic* 2019.09.004, DOI: 10.1016.

W. Vanderlinden, T. Brouns, P.U. Walker, P.J. Kolbeck, L.F. Miles, W. Ott, P.C. Nickels, Z. Debyser, and J. Lipfert (2019). The Free Energy Landscape of Retroviral Integration. *NatureComm*, 2019, 10: 4738.

A. Löf, P.U. Walker, S. M. Sedlak, S. Gruber, T. Obser, M.A. Brehm. M. Benoit, and J. Lipfert (2019). Multiplexed Protein Force Spectroscopy Reveals Equilibrium Protein Folding Dynamics and the Low-force Response of von Willebrand Factor. *PNAS*, 2019, Doi: 10.1073/1901794116.

A. Oberhofer, E. Reithmann, P. Spieler, W.L. Stepp, D. Zimmermann, B. Schmidt, E. Frey, and Z. Ökten (2020). Molecular Underspining of Cytoskeletal Cross-Talk. *PNAS*, 2020, doi: 10.1073/1917964117.

M. Striebel, I.R. Graf, and E. Frey (2020). A Mechanistic View of Collective Filament Motion in Active Nematic Networks. *BiophysJ*, 2020, 118: 313-324.

K. Ott, L. Martini, J. Lipfert, and U. Gerland (2020). Dynamics of the Buckling Transition in Double-Stranded DNA and RNA. *BiophysJ*, 2020, 118: 1690-1701.

W. Vanderlinden, P.J. Kolbeck, F. Kriegel, P.U. Walker, and J. Lipfert (2020). A Benchmark Data set for the Mechanical Properties of Double-Stranded DNA and RNA under Torsional Constraint. *Elsevier*, 2020, doi.org: 10.1016/j.dib.2020.105404.

T. Zettl, X. Shi, S. Bonilla, S.M. Sedlack, J. Lipfert, and D. Herschlag (2020). The Structural Ensemble of a Holliday Junction Determined by X-ray Scattering Interference. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 2020, doi: 10.1093/nar/gkaa509.

Abstract

The DNA four-way (Holliday) junction is the central intermediate of genetic recombination, yet key aspects of its conformational and thermodynamic properties remain unclear. While multiple experimental approaches have been used to characterize the canonical X-shape conformers under specific ionic conditions, the complete conformational ensemble of this motif, especially at low ionic conditions, remains largely undetermined. In line with previous studies, our single-molecule Förster resonance energy transfer (smFRET) measurements of junction dynamics revealed transitions between

two states under high salt conditions, but smFRET could not determine whether there are fast and unresolvable transitions between distinct conformations or a broad ensemble of related states under low and intermediate salt conditions. We therefore used an emerging technique, X-ray scattering interferometry (XSI), to directly probe the conformational ensemble of the Holliday junction across a wide range of ionic conditions. Our results demonstrated that the four-way junction adopts an out-of-plane geometry under low ionic conditions and revealed a conformational state at intermediate ionic conditions previously undetected by other methods. Our results provide critical information to build toward a full description of the conformational landscape of the Holliday junction and underscore the utility of XSI for probing conformational ensembles under a wide range of solution conditions.

J. Denk and, E. Frey (2020). Pattern-Induced Local Symmetry Breaking in Active-Matter Systems. PNAS, 2020, doi: 10.1073/pnas.2010302117.

H. Pandey, E. Reithmann, A. Goldstein-Levitin, J. Al-Bassam, E. Frey, L. Gheber (2021). Drag-Induced Directionality Switching of Kinesin-5 Cin8 Revealed by Cluster-Motility Analysis. SciAdv, 2021, 7: eabc1687.

A. Sciortino, and A.R. Bausch (2021). Pattern Formation and Polarity Sorting of Driven Actin Filaments on Lipid Membranes. PNAS, 2021, 118: 6 e2017047118.

Abstract

Collective motion of active matter is ubiquitously observed, ranging from propelled colloids to flocks of bird, and often features the formation of complex structures composed of agents moving coherently. However, it remains extremely challenging to predict emergent patterns from the binary interaction between agents, especially as only a limited number of interaction regimes have been experimentally observed so far. Here, we introduce an actin gliding assay coupled to a supported lipid bilayer, whose fluidity forces the interaction between self-propelled filaments to be dominated by steric repulsion. This results in filaments stopping upon binary collisions and eventually aligning nematically. Such a binary interaction rule results at high densities in the emergence of dynamic collectively moving structures including clusters, vortices, and streams of filaments. Despite the microscopic interaction having a nematic symmetry, the emergent structures are found to be polar, with filaments collectively moving in the same direction. This is due to polar biases introduced by the stopping upon collision, both on the individual filaments scale as well as on the scale of collective structures. In this context, positive half-charged topological defects turn out to be a most efficient trapping and polarity sorting conformation.

2.2 Topic 2. Research topics in Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences in Košice

Project 1. Development of efficient genetically encoded photosensitizers.

Project objective: The principal goal of this project is to develop a molecular method by which we will be able to transform unrelated flavoproteins into efficient photosensitizers producing singlet oxygen with a high quantum yield.

Principal Investigator: doc. RNDr. Erik Sedlák, DrSc.

Project 2. Aggregation of immunoglobulins and prediction of their colloidal stability using advanced kinetic analysis

Project objective: Stability of immunoglobulins G (IgGs) is one of the most critical properties affecting the success of the clinical application of immunotherapeutics. Obtaining correct parameters which describe the stability and aggregation of IgG is certainly a very ambitious goal mostly due to the complexity of their structures. In this project, our group will develop a biophysical model, which will be based on the analysis of IgG inactivation kinetics and microcalorimetry at elevated temperatures.

Principal Investigator: RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, PhD.

Project 3. Understanding IgG inactivation mechanism using single Hsp70 chaperone molecules and laser optical tweezers (Hsp70sensor)

Project objective: Structural and biochemical complexity of IgGs, as well as unclear inactivation mechanism, provide a significant hurdle for their accelerated development and their use in the clinical applications. In particular, the major concern during early stages of research and development is a natural tendency of antibodies to lose their efficacy by unproductive protein-protein association, which is likely triggered by the local unfolding of certain critical parts of the IgG structure. In this project we will develop a new sensor based on the Hsp70 chaperone with functionality that enable monitoring the generation of the aggregation-prone states of IgG and its fragments.

Principal Investigator: RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, PhD.

CIB Publications and selected abstracts of scientific publications:

Siposova K.*, Huntosova V.*, Garcarova I., Shlapa Y., Timashkov I., Belous A., Musatov A.: Dual-Functional Antioxidant and Antiamyloid Cerium Oxide Nanoparticles Fabricated by Controlled Synthesis in Water-Alcohol Solutions. *Biomedicines*, 10(5):942 (2022)

Máčajová M., Huntošová V.*, Meta M., Kundeková B., Bilčík B*.: Quail Chorioallantoic Membrane – A Tool for Photodynamic Diagnosis and Therapy. *Journal of Visualized Experiments*, e63422 (2022)

Dušeková E., Berta M., Sedláková D., Reha D., Dzurillová V., Shaposhnikovam A., Fadaei F., Tomková M., Minofar B., Sedlák E*.: Specific anion effect on properties of HRV 3C protease. *Biophysical Chemistry*, 287:106825 (2022)

Abstract

Specific salts effect is intensively studied from the prospective of modification of different physico-chemical properties of biomacromolecules. Limited knowledge of the specific salts effect on enzymes led us to address the influence of five sodium anions: sulfate, phosphate, chloride, bromide, and perchlorate, on catalytic and conformational properties of human rhinovirus-14 (HRV) 3C protease. The enzyme conformation was monitored by circular dichroism spectrum (CD) and by tyrosines fluorescence. Stability and flexibility of the enzyme have been analyzed by CD in the far-UV region, differential scanning calorimetry and molecular dynamics simulations, respectively. We showed significant influence of the anions on the enzyme properties in accordance with the Hofmeister effect. The HRV 3C protease in the presence of kosmotropic anions, in contrast with chaotropic anions, exhibits increased stability, rigidity. Correlations of stabilization effect of anions on the enzyme with their charge density and the rate constant of the enzyme with the viscosity B-coefficients of anions suggest direct interaction of the anions with HRV 3C protease. The role of stabilization and decreased fluctuation of the polypeptide chain of HRV 3C protease on its activation in the presence of kosmotropic anions is discussed within the frame of the macromolecular rate theory.

Gala M., Pristas P., Zoldak G*.: Allosteric inter-domain contacts in bacterial Hsp70 are located in regions that avoid insertion and deletion events. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23:2788 (2022)

Espina A., Sanchez-Cortes S., Jurasekova Z*.: Vibrational study (Raman, SERS, and IR) of plant gallnut polyphenols related to the fabrication of iron gall inks. *Molecules*, 27(1):279 (2022)

Jurasekova Z*., Jutkova A., Kozar T., Stanicova J*.: Vibrational characterization of the pesticide molecule Tebuconazole. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 268:120629 (2022)

Trosanova Z., Lousa P., Kozelekova A., Brom T., Gasparik N., Tungli J., Weisova V., Zupa E., Zoldak G., Hritz J*.: Quantitation of Human 14-3-3- ζ dimerization and the effect of phosphorylation on dimer-monomer equilibria. *Jmb* 434(7):167479 (2022)

Siposova K., Kozar T*., Stupakova M., Musatov A.: Complementary experimental and computational analysis of the effects of non-ionic detergents and phospholipids on insulin amyloid aggregation. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces*, 197:111428 (2021)

Abstract

Amphiphilic compounds, both detergents and lipids, are important tools for in vitro analysis of water-soluble and integral membrane proteins. A key question is whether these two groups of amphiphilic molecules use the same pathway to affect structural and functional integrity of proteins. In the present study, we tested the effect of non-ionic detergent dodecyl maltoside (DDM), two phospholipids, 1,2-dimyristoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC), 1,2-dihexanoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DHPC), and the detergent-phospholipid mixtures on insulin amyloidogenesis in vitro. Amyloidogenesis

of insulin is significantly affected by DDM in a time-and dose-dependent manner, but only slightly affected by either of phospholipids. Addition of DHPC or DMPC to detergent does not alter the inhibiting pattern, suggesting that DDM preferably binds to insulin. The molecular modeling revealed that DDM and the phospholipids occupy equivalent binding sites. DDM, due to the presence of maltose with several oxygen atoms (hydroxylic, glycosidic and ring) is involved in more hydrogen bonds than DHPC or DMPC. Hydrophobic interactions are important factors to stabilize both, DDM and phospholipids in their binding sites. Our results indicate that certain detergents (applying DDM as an example) and selected phospholipids are not always interchangeable in their use to investigate the effect of amphiphilic compounds on the behavior of amyloid-prone proteins.

Poropat S.F., Kundrat M., Mannion P.D., Upchurch P., Tischler T.R., Elliott D.A: Second specimen of the Late Cretaceous Australian sauropod dinosaur *Diamantinasaurus matildae* provides new anatomical information on the skull and neck of early titanosaurs. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, zlaa173 (2021)

Huntosova V.*, Horvath D., Seliga R., Wagnieres G.: Influence of Oxidative Stress on Time-Resolved Oxygen Detection by [Ru(Phen)₃]²⁺ In Vivo and In Vitro. *Molecules*, 26:485 (2021)

Mikulova L., Pechova I., Jancura D., Stupak M., Fabian M.*: Thermodynamics of the P-type Ferryl Form of Bovine Cytochrome c Oxidase. *Biochemistry (Moscow)*, 86:74-83 (2021)

Sedlak E., Kozar T., Varhac R., Musatov A., Tomaskova N.: Anion-Specific Effects on the Alkaline State of Cytochrome c. *Biochemistry (Moscow)*, 86:59-73 (2021)

Rendosova M., Gyepes R., Cigelova Maruscakova I., Mudronova D., Sabolova D., Kello M., Vilkova M., Almasi M., Huntosova V., Zemek O., Vargova Z.: An in vitro selective inhibitory effect of silver(i) aminoacidates against bacteria and intestinal cell lines and elucidation of the mechanism of action by means of DNA binding properties, DNA cleavage and cell cycle arrest. *Dalton Transactions*, 50:936-953 (2021)

Tomášková N., Novák P., Kožár T., Petrenčáková M., Jancura D., Yassaghi G., Man P., Sedlák E.*: Early modification of cytochrome c by hydrogen peroxide triggers its fast degradation. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 174:413-423 (2021)

Zeľeňáková A., Szűcsová J., Nagy L, Girman V., Zeľeňák V., Huntošová V.: Magnetic characterization and moderate cytotoxicity of magnetic mesoporous silica nanocomposite for drug delivery of naproxen. *nanomaterials*, 11:901 (2021)

Zoričák M., Horváth D., Gazda V., Hudec O.: Spatial evolution of industries modelled by cellular automata. *Journal of Business Research*, 129:580-588 (2021)

Garcia-Sanchez S., Gala M., Žoldák G.*: Nanoimpact in Plants : Lessons from the Transcriptome. *Plants*, 10, 751 (2021)

Skornova I., Simurda T., Stasko J., Horvath D., Zolkova J., Holly P., Brunclikova M., Samos M., Bolek T., Schnierer M., Slavik L, Kubisz P.: Use of fibrinogen determination methods in differential diagnosis of hypofibrinogenemia and dysfibrigenemia. *Clinical Laboratory*, 67:1028-1034 (2021)

Moskvin M., Huntosova V., Herynek V., Matous P., Michalcova A., Lobaz V., Zasonska B., Slouf M., Seliga R., Horak D.: In vitro cellular activity of maghemite/cerium oxide magnetic nanoparticles with antioxidant properties. *Colloids and Surface B: Biointerfaces*, 204:111824 (2021)

Sztachova T., Pechova I., Mikulova L., Stupak M., Jancura D., Fabian M.*: Peroxide stimulated transition between the ferryl intermediates of bovine cytochrome c oxidase. *BBA-Bioenergetics*, 1862:148447 (2021)

Džupponová V., Žoldák G.*: Salt-dependent passive adsorption of IgG1 κ -type monoclonal antibodies on hydrophobic microparticles. *Biophysical Chemistry*, 275:106609 (2021)

Abstract

Understanding how antibodies adsorb on solid surfaces is essential for developing effective approaches to control this process. In this study, passive adsorptions on the hydrophobic solid surface of a polystyrene microparticle (MP) of two highly similar IgG1 κ -type monoclonal antibodies (mAbs), rituximab, and trastuzumab, were examined in the presence of Hofmeister salts. Except of kosmotropic salts, the screening of electrostatic interactions using salts reduces the passive adsorption of mAbs on MP. To better understand the ion-specific adsorption process, salt-dependent Langmuir isotherm parameters were obtained and correlated for two mAbs. We find that while their maximum adsorption capacities to MPs are highly correlated ($r > 0.9$), the salt-dependent profiles of adsorption binding constants, K_{obs} , differ substantially. For rituximab, K_{obs} increases >10 -fold in an ion-specific manner; for trastuzumab, K_{obs} remains constant. We conclude that even minor sequence variations among the mAbs can affect the adsorption, as well as the molecular forces attracting proteins to a solid surface. This difference might originate from the heterogeneous orientation of the adsorbed mAbs.

Beňová E., Horenbecq V., Zeleňák V., Huntošová V., Almáši M., Máčajová M., Bergé-Lefranc D.: pH-responsive mesoporous silica drug delivery system, its biocompatibility and co-adsorption/co-release of 5-Fluorouracil and Naproxen. *Applied Surface Science*, 561:150011 (2021)

Agnolín F.L., Lu J.Ch., Kunderát M.*, Xu L.: Alvarezsaurid osteology: new data on cranial anatomy. *Historical Biology*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2021.1929203> (2021)

Horvath D.*, Tomkova S., Huntosova, V.*: Selection of Unique Molecules for Cancer Treatment by Distance-Based Method: Hypericin Effect on Respiratory Chain. *Biophysica*, 1:222-237 (2021)

Monfroy Q.T., Kunderat M.*: The osteohistological variability in the evolution of basal avialans. *Acta Zoologica*, 00:1-28 (2021)

Nemergut M., Skrabana R., Berta M., Pluckthun A., Sedlak E.*: Purification of MBP fusion proteins using engineered DARPIn affinity matrix. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 187:105-112 (2021)

Bano G., Kubackova J., Hovan A., Strejckova A., Ivanyi G.T., Vizsnyiczai G., Kelemen L., Zoldak G., Tomori Z., Horvath D.*: Power Spectral Density Analysis of Nanowire-Anchored Fluctuating Microbead Reveals a Double Lorentzian Distribution. *mathematics*, 9:1748 (2021)

Hovan A., Berta M., Sedlakova D., Miskovsky P., Bano G., Sedlak E.: Heme is responsible for enhanced singlet oxygendeactivation in cytochrome c. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 23:15557-15563 (2021)

Kundrat M.*, Cruickshank R.I.: New information on multispherulitic dinosaur eggs: Faveoolithidae and Dendroolithidae. *Historical Biology*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2021.1961764> (2021)

Monfroy Q.T., Kundrat M.*, Uesugi K., Hoshino M.: Dichotomy in formation and growth of bones of *Yanornis martini* (Pygostylia, Ornithuromorpha): study of thermal regime in an extinct bird. *Historical Biology*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2021.1960323> (2021)

Monfroy Q.T., Kundrat M.*, O'Connor J.K., Hai-Lu Y., Marone F., Stampanoni M., Smajda B.: Synchrotron microtomography-based osteohistology of *Gansus yumenensis*: new data on the evolution of uninterrupted bone deposition in basal birds. *Acta Zoologica*, 00: 1-27 (2021)

Sengupta A., Rognoni L.E., Merkel U., Zoldak G., Rief M.: SlyD Accelerates trans-to-cis Prolyl Isomerization in a Mechanosignaling Protein under Load. *Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 125 (31): 8712-8721 (2021)

Abstract

Prolyl isomerization is recognized as one of the key regulatory mechanisms, which plays a crucial role in cell signaling, ion channel gating, phage virus infection, and molecular timing. This isomerization is usually slow but often accelerated by an enzyme, called peptidyl-prolyl isomerase (PPIase). In the current project, we investigate using single-molecule force spectroscopy (SMFS) the impact of a bacterial PPIase, SlyD, on the cis-trans isomerization of the proline 2225 (P2225) in an isolated 20th domain of a cytoskeletal mechanosensing protein filamin-A (FlnA20). To explore the FlnA20-PPIase interaction, we have used multiple SMFS modes, like constant velocity, constant distance, and jumping trap experiments. In our previous study, we reported the unique nature of the P2225, which is conserved in all naturally occurring filamins and can slowly (minutes) interconvert between cis-trans isomers, in absence of any PPIase. Our current results show a staggering 25-fold acceleration of the trans-to-cis isomerization rate in the presence of saturating SlyD concentration (7.25 μ M) compared to the unenzymatic condition. A SlyD concentration-dependent depletion of the trans isomeric lifetime was also observed. Additionally, we observed that SlyD stabilizes the cis-isomer in the native state of FlnA20 by \sim 2 kBT. This is the first single-molecule observation of the cis-trans isomerization catalysis by a PPIase in a mechanosensing protein.

Gala M., Žoldák G.*: Classifying Residues in Mechanically Stable and Unstable Substructures Based on a Protein Sequence: The Case Study of the DnaK Hsp70 Chaperone. *nanomaterials*, 11(9):2198 (2021)

Kundrát M.*: Earliest migratory cephalic NC cells are potent to differentiate into dental ectomesenchyme of the two lungfish dentitions: tetrapodomorph ancestral condition of unconstrained capability of mesencephalic NC cells to form oral teeth. *The Science of Nature*, 108:37 (2021)

Eckert T., Jahrling-Butkus M., Loutin H., Burg-Roderfeld M., Zhang R., Zhang N., Hesse K., Petridis K.A., Kozar T., Steinmeyer J., Schauer R., Engelhard P., Kozarova A., Hudson J.W., Siebert H.Ch.: Efficacy of Chondroprotective Food Supplements Based on Collagen Hydrolysate and Compounds Isolated from Marine Organisms. *marine drugs*, 19(10): 542 (2021)

Huntosova V.*, Datta S., Lenkavská L., Macajová M., Bilčík B., Kundeková B., Cavarga I., Kronek J., Jutková A., Miskovský P., Jancura D.: Alkyl Chain Length in Poly(2-oxazoline)-Based Amphiphilic Gradient Copolymers Regulates the Delivery of Hydrophobic Molecules: A Case of the Biodistribution

and the Photodynamic Activity of the Photosensitizer Hypericin. *Biomacromolecules*, 22: 4199-4216 (2021)

Bauer J., Zoldak G.*: Interpretation of Single-Molecule Force Experiments on Proteins Using Normal Mode Analysis. *nanomaterials*, 11: 2795 (2021)

Shen C., Pegas R.V., Gao Ch., Kundrat M., Zhang L., Wei X., Zhou X.: A new specimen of *Sinopterus dongi* (Pterosauria, Tapejaridae) from the Jiufotang Formation (Early Cretaceous, China). *PeerJ*, 9:e12360 (2021)

Horvath D., Gazda J., Slapak E., Maksymyuk T., Dohler M.: Evolutionary Coverage Optimization for a Self-Organizing UAV-Based Wireless Communication System. *IEEEAccess*, 9:145066-145082 (2021)

Kubackova J., Slaby C., Horvath D., Hovan A., Ivanyi G.T, Vizsnyiczai G., Kelemen L., Zoldak G., Tomori Z., Bano G.: Assessing the Viscoelasticity of Photopolymer Nanowires Using a Three-Parameter Solid Model for Bending Recovery Motion. *nanomaterials*, 11:2961 (2021)

Pevna V., Wagnieres G., Huntosova V.*: Autophagy and Apoptosis Induced in U87 MG Glioblastoma Cells by Hypericin-Mediated Photodynamic Therapy Can Be Photobiomodulated with 808 nm Light. *biomedicines*, 9:1703 (2021)

3. POWERPOINT PRESENTATIONS UPJS

3.1 Research topics in Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences in Košice

See Annex

3.2 Protein folding and stability – human myeloma light chain proteins

See Annex

3.3 In silico protein evolution

See Annex

3.4 Utilization of ribosome display in directed evolution of haloalkane dehalogenase DhaA

See Annex

3.5 LOV2 domain as photosensitizer in photodynamic therapy

See Annex

